

NocMaker : A cross-platform open-source design space exploration tool for networks on chip

David Castells-Rufas¹, Jaume Joven¹, Sergi Risueño¹,
Eduard Fernandez¹, Jordi Carrabina¹

¹ Cephis –Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Spain
{david.castells, jaume.joven}@uab.es, {srisueno, efernandez}@microelec.uab.es,
jordi.carrabina@uab.es

Extended Abstract

1 Introduction

Networks on chip have been proposed to overcome the limitations of bus-based systems in complex Systems on Chip [1] like many-core processors. NoCs are superior in terms of performance, energy efficiency, and scalability while boosting design productivity by reusing large silicon blocks like processors, and network elements.

Network design tools should be able to create networks with different design space parameters and determine their system metrics but they should also validate them, identifying design errors and system bottlenecks. Given some system requirements, the tools should help in changing the values of different design space parameters and determine the obtained results. This process is what we know as design space exploration. The need for such tools is identified as challenge 3.5 in the HIPEAC roadmap [2].

This work presents the tool NocMaker, which is used for NoC design space exploration, NoC generation, and system validation. NocMaker is available at <http://cephis.uab.es/proj/public/nocmaker/index.xhtml> as Open Source under Apache2 license.

Some early approaches [3],[4] used standard network simulators like OPNET or NS-2 to build abstract NoC models, which were useful to obtain performance metrics but could not be used to estimate area or power consumption. To get this kind of detail some tools create HDL descriptions of the network elements. This is the case of xPipes [5], NoCGen [6], and others that use parametrizable HDL templates at the RTL design level that are instantiated and combined to get the final design. RTL designs are convenient for NoC synthesis but are slow to simulate. Higher abstraction models based on SystemC and TLM design level can offer faster simulation times (like in [7]), but then it is difficult to extract area information and synthesis is more complex and too much dependent on the quality of synthesis tools. Some frameworks take the option to maintain several models at different levels of abstraction so that simulation is fast and synthesis is more deterministic. But this is non-desirable since maintaining models synchronized is difficult and error prone. Another option to boost simulation performance is to use cycle accurate HDL models and hardware emulation as presented in [8].

In order to determine network performance, statistical traffic pattern generators have been widely used, but they tend to be very different from traffic patterns observed in real systems. It is more convenient to work with real traffic patterns produced by real processors, which is usually prohibitive, or at least with realistic traffic patterns produced by simulation frameworks like MPARM [10] or other abstract CPU models [11].

For each network design, tools must extract some metrics like performance, area, and power consumption. Most tools are capable to obtain values like total throughput, mean latency, and aggregate bandwidth. Some tools like Maia [13] visualize link usage to help determine hotspots. Area usage can be obtained without simulation. There are two main approaches to measure it: 1) Use hardware synthesis ([9]), but place & route tools are too slow. 2) Synthesize some basic elements and infer the whole system area from the observed values ([15],[16]).

Energy consumption is more complex to measure because we basically need the whole system structure information but also the system dynamic information, which is obtained by simulation. Four approaches can be used: 1) Measure the real circuit energy consumption. 2) Use power analysis tools from the technology provider to analyze the whole system. 3) Use power analysis tools to analyze parts of the system and infer a cost function (as done in [9]). 4) Use a predefined library like Orion [17] or INTACTE [18] and system activity as the basis for energy consumption estimation. The last two approaches are faster than the first two because they do not need to go through power analysis tools for each different design, so they are more suitable for design space exploration.

2 NoC Modeling

JHDL [19], is a HDL environment based on Java. There are some good reasons to use JHDL as a modeling language for NoCs: 1) Circuits can dynamically change their interface using the `addPort` and `removePort` functions. This unique feature allows to efficiently designing system elements (like switches) that get rid of unused elements and ports. 2) Block construction can be parameterized by complex arguments (like our NDSP), simplifying the context information needed by the module creators and enabling the design of powerful traffic generation modules. 3) Custom state viewers can be developed to provide a much richer interpretation of system state than waveforms. 4) Simulation is interactive. 5) Java is cross-platform.

The NoC design space can be viewed as a multidimensional space. We define a Java class to represent Noc Design Space Points (NDSP). NoCMaker use objects of this class to create and handle their respective NoC instantiations. Although NDSPs can be retrieved from XML, they can also be created by going through a graphical user interface with a guided set of steps, that we call Wizard. A NDSPs object is used by the building process to create all the necessary logic elements. The resulting model is a fully functional, cycle accurate, and synthesizable HDL model. Currently NoCMaker supports a limited area of the huge design space. For instance switching modes are limited to wormhole, and ephemeral circuit switching. Network Interfaces are only available for Avalon, OPB, and abstract 32/64bits buses.

attached to each link of the network so that traffic traversing the link can be presented graphically (see Fig. 4). This approach has been previously applied in other works (like [20]), but NocMaker presents this information during interactive simulations, which helps to understand the dynamics of the system.

JHDL encourages the use of the structural level of design. The result of this process is a hierarchy of logic circuits whose leaves are primitive logic elements. If each JHDL primitive logic element is assigned a number real logic elements (LEs) or an equivalent gate count, the area usage of a circuit can be computed by summing up all their leaves. Although this approach is quite simplistic, it is useful for design space exploration since the early area estimations of different designs are proportional to area usage of their real synthesized versions (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 5. JHDL interactive schematic view of a router.

Fig. 6. Predicted and real LE usage for different routers of a 3x3 mesh NoC.

Obtaining early power estimates is more complex than obtaining area estimates. Again, in design space exploration, it is not crucial that the estimations match the observed real ones, but that the proportionality is maintained. To manage the problem we only look at the dynamic part of the power consumption, which can be simplified by the following expression (1), where C_i is the driven load capacitance, and α_i is the number of level swings at wire i .

$$P_{dyn} = V_{dd}^2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n C_i \alpha_i \quad (1) \quad C_i = F_i (C_g + C_w) \quad (2)$$

Load capacitance (C_i) is determined by the gate capacitance (C_g) of all nodes connected to wire i , and the wiring capacitance among them. The fan-out (F_i) is the number of nodes connected to wire i . For intra-router wiring we make the assumption that wire length is proportional to the fan-out, or in other words, that each connected node is connected directly to its driving node through a non-shared wire with capacitance C_w . Clock distribution makes a major contribution to the overall energy consumption, so clock wires have different capacitance parameters (C_{clk}). The capacity of inter-router wires is determined by C_{link} . In NocMaker C_g , C_w , C_{clk} , and C_{link} are determined as parameters of the design space. F_i is obtained by circuit hierarchy structure analysis, and α_i is found during simulation by using the `Wire.getTransitionCount` method. This simple approach can be used to compare different NoC designs or to create a power breakdown of a given design.

4 Circuit Validation and Synthesis

Network on chip building parts are mainly Routers and Network Interfaces (NI). These circuits can be fairly simple and easy to independently verify. However, when several modules are combined to form a network on chip, verification becomes very complex. A simple 4x4 mesh NoC, for instance, has 80 communication links among routers. If each link has 32 data bits and two control bits the number of wires that interconnect the routers is 2720. Analyzing the behavior of such a system at the inter-router level with classical waveform analysis becomes impossible as, after grouping 32 data bits, you still have 240 waveforms to look at. Moreover, the network dynamics is crucial in the appearance of errors. The problems that can arise can involve several flits at several different routers, or could be triggered when a very specific traffic pattern has occurred at a certain region of the NoC.

A set of techniques is proposed to tackle this high complexity. 1) Registering the time of the packet transmission and reception events in the processor models allows to compute performance information like point to point mean latency and bandwidth (as shown in **Fig. 3**) but also to present the packet communication in a timeline, so that the cause of big latencies can be identified (see **Fig. 2**). 2) a graphical view of the NoC topology (**Fig. 4**) can be used to give quick information of the routing decisions and flow control status, which are two common causes of NoC failures. In this diagram a router is drawn as a box with their respective input and output ports. A line inside the box connecting an input and an output is used to indicate that this route has been established. A color code is used to inform about the state of each link regarding flow control. 3) Detailed information from the internal circuits state can be visualized with classic JHDL facilities, the circuit browser, the interactive schematic view (**Fig. 5**), which presents all the values of the circuit wires in real time during simulation, and the waveform view. 4) Assertions can be inserted in behavioral circuits so that the correctness of the system is constantly supervised. If some incorrect state occurs, the assertion code stops the simulation and pops up a message giving the necessary hints to the designer to identify the cause of the error. Combining all these techniques a designer can detect problems at a high level and successively go to deeper and deeper levels of detail to identify the final error causes and correct them.

As the result of the design space exploration process one would expect to come up with an optimal network model for a given scenario. The resulting design should be then implemented with the final technology. NocMaker uses JHDL for netlisting the network design. Although JHDL only includes an EDIF netlister we have developed a Verilog netlister so that the resulting implementation is more independent on technology. Several networks have been synthesized using this process, so fulfilling the need of a correct by construction approach to NoC synthesis.

5. Conclusions

We have proposed an open source java based framework for the design space exploration of networks on chip. NocMaker can be used to get early estimations of performance, area, and power as a basic for different network evaluation, avoiding the

need to go through slow synthesis process. The use of a cycle accurate NoC model permits a very accurate performance estimation and allows a very early area usage estimation by primitive resource counting. Early power estimation is also possible thanks to the JHDL capacity to track wire activity and the ability to extract the fanout of each node of the system. The same tool has proven to be very valuable for network validation at different levels of abstraction.

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